

NEW MODIFICATION OF THE GEWALD REACTION FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF
SULFUR-CONTAINING, NUCLEIC BASE ANALOGS

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To my wonderful grandmother, Ada Faye Fine, who died of cancer in May 1996.

ABSTRACT

Heterocyclic compounds are some of the most interesting compounds in medicinal chemistry. Pyrimidine is a well known heterocyclic compound and is an important pharmacophore used in medicinal chemistry. Adenine and hypoxanthine-like frameworks structurally are consistent with the pyrimidine framework, showing immense promise in the development of biologically active compounds. Highly substituted 2-aminothiophenes are a class of compounds that are excellent scaffold motifs for the synthesis of biologically active compounds. Because they are used primarily as precursors, there is a lack of research concerning their biological activity. One of the approaches in medicinal chemistry is the fusion of multiple pharmacophores into one drug. This is thought to improve activity and reduce the risk of resistance to the drug formed by the cancer cells. Fusion of 2-aminothiophene and pyrimidine gives rise to compounds known as thiophene pyrimidines, which have great implications in the drug development field. It is known that Gewald reaction schemes give rise to 2-aminothiophenes and that cyclization generates a fusion between 2-aminothiophene and pyrimidine pharmacophores to produce thiophene pyrimidine derivatives. The synthesis of thiophene pyrimidines based on rigid monoketones was established and a one-pot reaction developed. This was used as a model for further reactions. The synthesis of thiophene pyrimidines based on flexible monoketones gave rise to a new modification of the classical Gewald reaction scheme. It allowed for the synthesis of 2-aminothiophenes easily and in acceptable yields for adenine-like compounds. The syntheses of compounds based on the hypoxanthine-like framework were not successful using the same reaction conditions. Instead, the hydrolysis and further cyclization of 2-aminothiophene derivatives from 3-cyano-2-aminothiophene derivatives allowed for the generation of hypoxanthine-like thiophene pyrimidine derivatives. A new method of synthesis for 2-aminothiophenes and thiophene pyrimidine derivatives was developed on the basis of rigid diketones. MTT assay of anticancer activity against HeLa cells and MCF-7 cells was used and it was found that 1.) compounds containing lipophilic, halogen substituents were the most active, and 2.) cyclization of 2-aminothiophenes to thiophene pyrimidines increased activity by nearly two-fold for majority of compounds. Compounds were screened for anti-microbial activity against gram positive (*S. pyogenes*, *S. epidermis*) and gram negative (*E. coli*, *P. fluorescens*) bacteria, but showed no significant activity. Compounds were also tested against *C. albicans*; while most showed no activity, m-Br and p-Br, hypoxanthine-like derivatives had significant activity. One

fluorinated compound was tested against *trypanosoma brucei* and showed no significant activity.

Keywords: Medicinal Chemistry, Pyrimidine, Thiophene, Cancer, Gewalt

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ABBREVIATIONS

5-FdUMP: 5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine-5'-monophosphate
5-FU: 5-fluorouracil
5-FUDP: 5-fluorouridine-5'-diphosphate
5-FUTP: 5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine-5'-triphosphate
CD₃OD: Deuterated Methanol
(CD₃)₂OD: Deuterated Acetone
DHFR: Dihydrofolate Reductase
DNA: Deoxyribonucleic Acid
DMSO-d₆: Deuterated Dimethyl Sulfoxide
dTTP: thymidine-5' triphosphate
GI₅₀: Growth Inhibitory Concentration
HMP: Hexose Monophosphate Pathway
MCR: Multicomponent Reaction
MIC: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration
MTT: (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide
RNA: Ribonucleic Acid
SAR: Structure Activity Relationships
TLC: Thin Layer Chromatography
TP: Thymidylate Synthase
UV: Ultraviolet

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. HETEROCYCLES IN MODERN DAY MEDICINAL CHEMISTRY

Heterocyclic compounds contain heteroatoms like sulfur, oxygen and nitrogen in addition to carbon to form an overall cyclic structure. This branch of compounds forms one of the largest classical divisions of organic chemistry.¹ Structurally, heterocycles are favorable in drug design because they act as important pharmacophores.² A pharmacophore describes the molecular features that are necessary for recognition of a ligand typically by a biological macromolecule. Designing compounds around these structures allows for the generation of novel structures while preserving and improving key biological interactions². The use of heterocyclic compounds in medicinal chemistry has been of great interest for both natural and synthetic drugs.²

An important characteristic that makes heterocyclic compounds interesting in the development of new medicinal agents is their role as biologically important molecules, such as vitamins, enzymes and nucleic acids.¹ This is due to the fact that heterocycles have a wide range of flexibility concerning its role in chemical reactions of the body. For example, some heterocycles form complexes with metal ions, while others contribute to the formation of nucleic bases in both DNA and RNA. Some heterocycles such as Vitamin C, E and B (Figure 1) are essential to biological processes as either coenzymes or their precursors. Some examples of B vitamins are folate, riboflavin and thiamine (Figure 1).¹

Figure 1: Structures of Vitamins C , E and B (including folate, riboflavin and thiamine).¹

Medicinally, heterocycles show great promise in development of new drugs for the treatments, which may include areas concerning anti-inflammatory,

antibacterial, antifungal, antimalarial, anticancer and many more.¹ This study was developed to concentrate on two varying heterocyclic like compounds, highly substituted 2-aminothiophenes and pyrimidine. Both types of compounds have the potential for immense biological significance in the development of new medicinal agents.^{3,4}

1.2 MEDICINAL SIGNIFICANCE OF PYRIMIDINE

Pyrimidine and purine derivatives are monocyclic and bicyclic heterocyclic compounds that are important for DNA as well as the coding of genetic information involving RNA.¹ A large number of medically important drugs contain the pyrimidine framework. A very important area of application for these frameworks is focused on chemotherapeutics, but many more applications are available.⁴

For antineoplastics and antitumor agents, wide arrays of pyridine and purine-based antimetabolites exist. These compounds are structurally similar to the endogenous substrates which they are intended to antagonize. Examples of some widely used pyrimidine-based antimetabolites are 5-fluorouracil (5-FU), azathioprine, mercaptopurine, thioguanine, and tegafur (Figure 2).⁴

Figure 2: Structural representations of antitumor and antineoplastic compounds that have pyrimidine and purine framework (Shown in purple).⁴

5-FU, first introduced in 1957, is a drug used for the treatment of solid tumors in colorectal, breast and gastrointestinal tract cancers. This compound works to occupy active sites of enzyme targets and interfere with the metabolism in malignant

cells. As given by the name, 5-FU is very similar in structure to uracil (Figure 3). The hydrogen in the five position of uracil is substituted for fluorine to produce 5-FU. One route of metabolism for 5-FU is the conversion to 5-FUTP (5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine-5'-triphosphate). Because of the similarity between Uridine-5'-triphosphate and 5-FUTP, it is taken up by RNA polymerase and ultimately leads to the incorporation of 5-FU into RNA. Another very important route of metabolic interference for 5-FU is its conversion to 5-FdUMP (5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine-5'-monophosphate) and subsequent inhibition of thymidylate synthase (TP) which has a pivotal role in the synthesis of DNA. Because of this decreases in the amount of dTTP (thymidine-5' triphosphate) available for DNA replication and repair, and programmed cell death is induced. Other potential mechanisms may be due to the integration of 5-FU into DNA and the synthesis of 5-FUDP (5-fluorouridine-5'-diphosphate) sugars into the membrane.⁵

Figure 3: Structure of uracil.⁵

Pyrimidine-based drugs are also important as antifolate, antibacterial, antifungal and antiprotozoal compounds. It was observed that certain types of pyrimidine based drugs can inhibit the enzyme dihydrofolate reductase (DHFR). Pyrimethamine is a drug that has strong activity against malarial plasmodia, where it also inhibits selectively DHFR (Figure 4).⁴

Figure 4: Structure of Pyrimethamine.⁴

Sulfa drugs sulfadiazine, sulfamerazine and sulfadimine are sulfonamides used to treat urinary tract infections, cerebrospinal meningitis and are involved in the eradication of bacteria in patients who have compromised immune systems; particularly individuals with impaired renal functions and individuals who are allergic to penicillin's (Figure 5).⁴

Figure 5: Structural representation of sulfa drugs.⁴

Antifungal properties are also a very attractive feature of drugs resembling the pyridine-based framework. Flucytosine is used for the treatment of serious systemic fungal infections generally caused by certain strains of *Candida* and *Cryptococcus*, while aphthous ulcerations are readily treated with a compound known as Hexitidine (Figure 6).⁴

Figure 6: Structural representation of antifungal drugs.⁴

The development of many drugs on the basis of the pyridine framework has shown the wide scope of medicinal significance of these types of compounds. Pyrimidine-based frameworks have the ability to be incorporated, with the right design, into many different types of drugs that target such a wide variety of diseases.⁴ Properties of pyrimidine framework show great promise for our study searching for anti-cancer, anti-fungal, anti-bacterial and anti-parasitic drugs.

1.3 MEDICINAL SIGNIFICANCE OF 2-AMINOTHIOPHENE

Highly functionalized 2-aminothiophenes (Figure 7) are important in the field of synthetic chemistry for the following reasons. Mostly, 2-aminothiophenes act as precursors to a broad range of synthetic pathways that ultimately produce many types of biologically active compounds. A great benefit of these scaffold motifs is that they are conveniently available through a versatile synthetic route known as the Gewald reaction scheme that involves the condensation of a ketone or aldehyde with an activated nitrile and elemental sulfur (Figure 8).⁶ The thiophene core exists in many natural and synthetic pharmaceuticals in which it is known that the thiophene core acts as a bioisostere for phenyl groups.⁷ Compounds that are bioisosteric to one another have similarities between physical and chemical properties. One biological application of 2-aminothiophene derivatives is their use as A₁ adenosine receptor allosteric enhancers.³

Figure 7: Structural representation of highly functionalized 2-aminothiophene and its thiophene core (highlighted in purple).³

Figure 8: Classical Gewald Reaction scheme featuring the condensation of a ketone or aldehyde with an activated nitrile and elemental sulfur under basic conditions.³

Many important pharmaceuticals have been derived from 2-aminothiophenes.³ Potent antitumor compounds were developed on the basis of thieno[2,3-b]azepin-4-one frameworks (Figure 9), while cinnamyl derivatives (Figure 10) of thieno[2,3-d]oxazinones have been shown to inhibit herpes protease processing in HSV-2 infected cells.^{8,9} The RNA polymerase holoenzyme has been a suitable target for antibacterial agents. One example of these agents is 2-ureido-thiophene-3-carboxylate (Figure 11) which has shown to possess low micromolar activity as inhibitors against *Staphylococcus aureus*.¹⁰

R¹=R²=Me

R¹= Ph R²=Me R³=Tosyl or Benzoyl

Figure 9: Potent antitumor compounds were developed on the basis of thieno[2,3-b]azepin-4-one frameworks.⁸

R=H, 2-Cl, 2-Br, 2-Me, 2-NO₂, 2-EtO, 4-CHO

Figure 10: Herpes proteases HSV-2 based on thieno[2,3-d]oxazinone frameworks.⁹

Figure 11: 2-ureido-thiophene-3-carboxylate an inhibitor against *Staphylococcus aureus*.¹⁰

Surprisingly, not much research has explored the biological significance of 2-aminothiophenes as lead compounds themselves, rather, as mention above, research surrounds the use of these compounds as precursors. One of the few studies shows that thiophene based derivatives may hinder malignant tumor growth via the hexose mono-phosphate (HMP) pathway,¹¹ but relevant research has not been explored for the activity of these compounds. A study done previously in our group identified 2-aminopyrroles as very important, novel pharmacophores (Figure 12).¹² As there is a great deal of similarity in structure between 2-aminopyrroles and 2-aminothiophenes we wanted to determine whether or not 2-aminothiophenes are a potential pharmacophore (Figure 12).

Figure 12: 2-aminopyrrole and 2-aminothiophene framework.¹²

1.4. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE COMBINATION OF PHARMACOPHORES OF PYRIMIDINE AND 2-AMINOTHIOPHENES, THIOPHENE PYRIMIDINE AND THEIR TARGETS

In the development of new biologically active compounds many different techniques are employed to improve activity of existing compounds for both synthetic and natural derivatives. One of these techniques involves the fusion of two pharmacophores. Combination of pyrimidine and 2-aminothiophene pharmacophores has been explored for biological significance.¹³ When these compounds are fused they give rise to thiophene pyrimidine analogs (Figure 13). Thiophene pyrimidines are used as bioisosteres of purine nucleobases such as adenine (Figure 14) and hypoxanthine (Figure 14).¹⁴ These compounds possess a wide range of anti-inflammatory, antitumor, antimalarial and antimicrobial biological activities.¹³ Regarding antitumor activity, some thiophene pyrimidine derivatives have shown to be potent multitargeted tyrosine kinase inhibitors,^{6,16} while others have been identified as inhibitors of human farnesyl pyrophosphate synthase.¹⁴ Further research suggests that thiophene pyrimidine bisphosphonate inhibitors have low nanomolar activity against bone related metastases.¹⁵ Also, thiophene pyrimidine derivatives have also been of interest as having antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *B. cereus*.¹³ Antifungal activity has also been explored against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*.¹³ Results from the investigations suggest that thiophene pyrimidine derivatives exhibit high biological activity against human pathogenic bacteria and phytopathogenic fungi.¹³

Figure 13: Fusion of thiophene core (I) with pyrimidine framework (II) gives rise to thiophene pyrimidine-based analogs (III).¹²

Figure 14: Framework of Thiophene Pyrimidine Derivatives and Structures of Adenine and Hypoxanthine.²

Heterocyclic compounds have been of great interest in the area of medicinal chemistry as such, the fusion of 2-aminothiophene and pyrimidine may prove to have immense biological significance. Research that has already explored thiophene pyrimidine analogs suggests that hypoxanthine-like and adenine-like frameworks show broad medicinal properties. This study was designed to explore the 2-

aminothiophene framework as a novel pharmacophore and to design aryl-based analogs on the basis of thiophene pyrimidine framework.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1. CHEMICAL SYNTHESIS

2.1.1. SYNTHESIS OF 2-AMINOTHIOPHENE AND THIOPHENE PYRIMIDINE DERIVATIVES ON THE BASIS OF RIGID MONOKETONES

The Gewald reaction was made primarily for alkyl type of ketones.⁵ However, several modifications of the classical conditions, particularly of the type of base used, have given a wider range of applicability to the Gewald general reaction scheme (Figure 15). The proposed mechanism of Gewald reaction scheme according to literature data denotes the first stage of the reaction as a Knoevenagel-Cope condensation. The reaction that produces substituted 2-aminothiophenes occurs in three, base-promoted steps: condensation of starting substrates to compound 3; and addition of sulfur to the alpha, beta-unsaturated nitrile as illustrated as compound 4 and finally a ring-closure of the ylidene-sulfur adduct 4 to yield highly substituted 2-aminothiophenes.³ The proposed mechanism of cyclization of 2-aminothiophene to thiophene pyrimidine is not well understood.

Figure 15: The proposed reaction mechanism of the Gewald reaction.⁵

Rigid monoketones were used as starting material in a reaction to generate a model for flexible monoketones and rigid diketones to test the variability of the reaction conditions and to target aromatic mechanisms. By increasing the variability of the reaction, a library can be developed to yield novel compounds. Reaction modifications using inorganic bases have good appeal due to their strength, which typically decreases the overall reaction time. Inorganic catalysts also worked exceptionally well with a class of compounds that were previously synthesized in our group that have similar frameworks to that of 2-aminothiophenes and thiophene pyrimidines.¹¹ The pharmacophores based on highly substituted 2-aminothiophene structure in combination with pyrimidine framework were explored. The designed frameworks were synthesized using a multicomponent reaction (MCR) approach. MCR's are described as the combination of three or more reactants combined in one

pot that react simultaneously with one another to produce desired products of interest. Utilization of MCR's are very useful in terms of time economy and because of this they allow for the easy synthesis of a library of compounds in high yields.

Compound 1 (Figure 17) was initially synthesized in several steps by various authors. Moeinpour et al synthesized the 2-aminothiophene via a modification of the classical Gewald reaction, where cesium carbonate was utilized as a catalyst.¹⁷ The reaction was repeated to yield a total of 81% of 2-aminothiophene (Figure 16). Initially the synthesis of compound 1 was made by Pfeiffer et al. which was repeated to yield 71% product (Figure 17).¹⁸ The complied yield for both steps was equivalent to a total yield of 69%. Both reaction conditions were combined and optimized in order to produce the compound in a four-component, one-pot reaction (Figure 18). Table 1 describes reaction condition optimization.

Figure 16: Synthetic scheme carried out by Moeinpour et al.¹⁷

1

Figure 17: Synthetic scheme carried out by Pfeiffer et al. to synthesize compound 1.¹⁸

1

Figure 18: Multicomponent reaction to produce compound 1.

Catalyst	Yield	Reaction Conditions
Li ₂ CO ₃	23.8%	3 mL Formamide, 90°C-16hrs, 210°C-20 min
K ₂ CO ₃ granulated	0%	3 mL Formamide, 90°C-16hrs, 210° C-20 min
K ₂ CO ₃ ungranulated	50%	3 mL Formamide, 90°C-16hrs, 210° C-20 min
Na ₂ CO ₃	8%	3 mL Formamide, 90°C-16hrs, 210° C-20 min
Cs ₂ CO ₃	40%	3 mL Formamide, 90°C-16hrs, 210° C-20 min
Na ₂ CO ₃	0%	3 mL Formamide, 90°C-16hrs, 150° C-1 hr → 210 C ⁰ -20 min
Cs ₂ CO ₃	0%	3 mL Formamide, 90°C-16hrs, 150° C-1 hr → 210 C ⁰ -20 min
Cs ₂ CO ₃	0%	3 mL Formamide, 90°C-16hrs, 150° C-1 hr → 210 C ⁰ -20 min
Na ₂ CO ₃	0%	3 mL Formamide, 90°C-16hrs, 150° C-1 hr → 210 C ⁰ -20 min
Na ₂ CO ₃	43%	3 mL Formamide, 90°C-16hrs, 210° C-1 hr
Li ₂ CO ₃	0%	3 mL Formamide, 90°C-16hrs, 210° C-1 hr
K ₂ CO ₃ ungranulated	87%	3 mL Formamide, 90°C-16hrs, 210° C-1 hr

Table 1: Optimization of reaction conditions of compound 1 in one-pot synthesis.

As a result, compound 1 was synthesized in one-pot reaction for the first time with an 87% yield with commercially available reactants.

2.1.2. SYNTHESIS OF 2-AMINOTHIOPHENE AND THIOPHENE PYRIMIDINE DERIVATIVES ON THE BASIS OF FLEXIBLE MONOKETONES: ADENINE-LIKE DERIVATIVES

Acetophenone derivatives were utilized to generate a library on the basis of the MCR reaction from the rigid monoketone optimization using cyclohexanone. Classical Gewald conditions (Figure 19) proved to be unsuccessful for the production of 2-aminothiophenes based on acetophenone, adenine-like derivatives. This may have been due to the poor solubility of the intermediate formed by the ketone and malononitrile (Figure 20). In a solvent like ethanol, the intermediate precipitates out and quenches the reaction. The use of ethanol appears to promote the formation of side reactions, reducing the amount of desired product that is formed. Pyridine was therefore utilized as a reaction solvent to alleviate issues concerned with solubility of the intermediate. Another reason may be due to the deactivation of the carbonyl group in acetophenone from the aromatic ring to compare with aliphatic ketones. Because of this, the alpha-hydrogens next to the carbonyl are less likely to be deprotonated, ultimately delaying, if not quenching, the overall reaction progress. Reaction conditions were optimized as described in Table 2.

Figure 19: Classical Gewald Reaction scheme featuring the condensation of a ketone with an activated nitrile and elemental sulfur under basic conditions (morpholine or Et₂NH).⁵

Figure 20: Intermediate produced by the condensation of acetophenone and malononitrile.

Solvent	Base	Base Equivalents	Reagent Equivalents	Reaction Conditions
Ethanol	Cs ₂ CO ₃	0.13 → 0.5	1.0, 1.1, 1.0	Reaction did not complete
Ethanol	K ₂ CO ₃	0.13 → 0.5	1.0, 2.2, 2.0	Reaction did not complete
Ethanol	Et ₂ NH	0.13 → 0.5	1.0, 2.2, 2.0	Reaction did not complete
Ethanol	Morpholine	0.13 → 1.0	1.0, 2.2, 2.0	Reaction did not complete
Ethanol	Piperdine	0.13 → 1.0	1.0, 2.2, 2.0	Reaction did not complete
Ethanol	Et ₃ NH	0.13 → 1.0	1.0, 2.2, 2.0	Reaction did not complete
Pyridine	Cs ₂ CO ₃	0.5	1.0, 2.2, 2.0	90°C, 16 hours
Pyridine	Cs ₂ CO ₃	0.5	1.0, 2.2, 2.0	115°C, 6 hours

Table 2: Optimization of reaction conditions for the synthesis of compound 2.

The modifications of conditions for compound 2 are listed in Table 2. The reaction conditions were subsequently optimized by utilization of differing bases. Carbonates of alkali metals were explored and produced very low yields, which was probably because due to the promotion of side reactions. A benefit to using organic bases is that they are more sterically hindered and work more effectively as a softer base. The organic base of particular interest was pyridine, which showed to work as both the base and the solvent.

Compound	Base	Reaction Conditions	Yield
	Cs ₂ CO ₃ (0.5 mmol)	Pyridine	15%
	Li ₂ CO ₃ (0.5 mmol)	115°C 6 hours	22.5%
	Na ₂ CO ₃ (0.5 mmol)		17.5%
	K ₂ CO ₃ (0.5 mmol)		9.2%
	Pyridine		50%

Table 3: Optimization of initial reaction conditions using varying bases.

Figure 21: Synthetic scheme for synthesis of compound 2.

Figure 22: Synthetic scheme for synthesis of compound 10.

By utilizing the reaction conditions which demonstrated the best performance illustrated above (Figures 21 and 22), we were able to generate a library on the basis of 2-aminothiophene and thiophene pyrimidine framework for flexible aromatic monoketones. A library was generated in order to analyze structure activity relationships (SAR) which describes the interaction of the drug with its target. SAR can help understand what important features are necessary for optimal binding and in turn the best possible biological activity. The table listed below shows compounds synthesized based on 2-aminothiophene compounds and their corresponding thiophene pyrimidine derivatives (Figure 23).

Figure 23: A library of 2-aminothiophenes and thiophene pyrimidine derivatives was synthesized on the basis of adenine.

Compound	Reaction Conditions	Yield
<p>2</p>	Pyridine 115°C 6 hours	50%
<p>3</p>	Pyridine 115°C 2 hours	46%
<p>4</p>	Pyridine 115°C 2 hours	45%

Table 4: Adenine-like compounds synthesized, reaction conditions and their yields (Continued on page 16).

5		Pyridine 115°C 2 hours	47%
6		Pyridine 115°C 2 hours	57%
7		Pyridine 115°C 4 hours	30%
8		Pyridine 115°C 4 hours	45%
9		Pyridine 115°C 2 hours	44%
10		Formamide 210°C 2 hours	61%

Table 4: Adenine-like compounds synthesized, reaction conditions and their yields (Continued on page 17).

11		Formamide 210°C 2 hours	67%
12		Formamide 210°C 2 hours	64%
13		Formamide 210°C 2 hours	67%
14		Formamide 210°C 2 hours	68%
15		Formamide 210°C 2 hours	42%
16		Formamide 210°C 3 hours	46%

Table 4: Adenine-like compounds synthesized, reaction conditions and their yields (Continued on page 18).

17	Formamide 210°C 2 hours	52%

Table 4: Adenine-like compounds synthesized, reaction conditions and their yields.

The reactions for derivatives that were substituted with halogens ran quickly and relatively clean and with good yields. It should be noted that relatively lower yields are attributed to the cyclization of compound 2 to another side product, thieno[2,3-*b*]pyridine-5-carbonitrile, 4,6-diamino-3-phenyl (Figure 24). In literature it has been shown that this side product is formed in the excess of malononitrile.¹⁹ Because the reaction needs an excess of malononitrile and sulfur to run to completion, the side product cyclization affects the yield of the 2-aminothiophene. This is observed for all 2-aminothiophenes synthesized. The synthesis of the side product compound was confirmed both with NMR analysis as well as literature based sources (Figure 24).¹⁹

Figure 24: Continued cyclization of compound 2 (I) in the presence of excess malononitrile to the side product (II). This is observed in all reactions done for adenine-like derivatives.¹⁹

A proposed mechanism for the side production cyclization is illustrated in figure 25. The excess of malononitrile reacts with excess base. This activated nitrile reacts with the 2-aminothiophene and next there is an attack from the amine which ultimately induces self-cyclization to yield a final product that cannot further react in the current reaction conditions.

Figure 25: The proposed mechanism by which compound 2 is converted into its corresponding side product.¹⁹

In conclusion, modification of the Gewald reaction allowed for incorporation of aromatic ketones into the synthesis of highly substituted 2-aminothiophene derivatives as well as the continued synthesis of compounds to their respective thiophene pyrimidine counterparts. Based on this scheme and the adenine-like framework, the synthesis of a library of compounds was completed. It was observed that side product cyclization results in the reduction of overall yield, which has not been noted in any previous literature sources.

2.1.3. SYNTHESIS OF 2-AMINOTHIOPHENE AND THIOPHENE PYRIMIDINE DERIVATIVES ON THE BASIS OF FLEXIBLE MONOKETONES: HYPOXANTHINE -LIKE DERIVATIVES

Pyrrole based compounds that have been previously synthesized based on a hypoxanthine-like framework have exhibited extraordinary anti-cancer activity in comparison to their adenine like counterparts (Figure 26).¹⁶ Initially, the reaction conditions used for the synthesis of the library for adenine-like compounds were utilized. These conditions were unsuccessful for the synthesis of desired 2-aminothiophene. Because of this, new approaches were employed. In literature, Schatz et al. made use of reaction conditions in which a mix of solvents, ethanol and diethylamine, were heated 50°C overnight (Figure 27).²⁰ In this reaction, diethylamine works as a base while also increasing the solubility of the intermediate. Unfortunately, these conditions were unsuccessful.

As mentioned earlier, the Gewald reaction is a MCR and because of this the intermediate can be synthesized using the first stage of the reaction (Figure 28) rather than complete synthesis to 2-aminothiophene. The classical synthesis of Knoevenagel-Cope condensation is between a ketone or an aldehyde in either acidic or basic conditions. The intermediate produced from the reaction is then added to elemental sulfur in basic conditions to produce 2-aminothiophene compounds. Because the condensation reaction involving acetophenone and cyanoacetamide only proceeds in the presence of acidic conditions, the one-pot synthesis for 2-aminothiophenes was shown to be not possible.²¹ Ultimately, the synthesis of the intermediate could not be easily generated and a different synthetic route to hypoxanthine-like derivatives was employed.

Figure 26: Structural differences between adenine and hypoxanthine.³

Figure 27: The reaction scheme from Schatz et al.²⁰

Figure 28: Synthesis of intermediate and then its subsequent conversion to 2-aminothiophene.³

Solvent	Catalyst	Catalyst equivalents	Reactant equivalents	Reaction Conditions
Pyridine	Morpholine	0.13→1.0	1,2,2,2	Overnight at 115°C, Unsuccessful
Pyridine	Cs ₂ CO ₃	0.13→0.5	1,2,2,2	Overnight at 115°C, Unsuccessful
Pyridine	Pyridine	As solvent	1,2,2,2	Overnight at 115°C, Unsuccessful
Ethanol	Et ₂ NH	1.0	1,2,2,2	48 hr reflux at 90°C, Unsuccessful
Ethanol	Morpholine	1.0	1,2,2,2	48 hr at 90°C, Unsuccessful
Ethanol	Et ₂ NH	0.13	1,2,2,2	72 hr at 90°C, Unsuccessful
Ethanol	Acetic Acid	0.13	1,2,2,2	72 hr at 90°C, Reaction did not complete
Acetic Acid	Acetic Acid	As solvent	1,2,2,2	72 hr at 90°C, Reaction did not complete

Table 5: Optimization of 2-aminothiophene, hypoxanthine-like compounds using acetophenone and cyanoacetamide.

Solvent	Catalyst	Catalyst equivalents	Reactant equivalents	Reaction Conditions
Acetic Acid	Acetic Acid	As Solvent	1.0,4.0	72 hr at 90°C Reaction did not complete
Acetic Acid	NH ₄ HO ₃	Catalytical→equimolar	1.0,1.0→1.0,4.0	72 hr at 90°C Reaction did not complete
Ethanol	K ₂ CO ₃	Catalytical→equimolar	1.0,4.0	72 hr at 90°C Reaction did not complete
Ethanol	Boric acid	0.5 mmol	1.0,1.0	72 hr at 90°C Reaction did not complete

Table 6: Optimization of intermediate for the synthesis of 2-aminothiophene, hypoxanthine-like compounds.

Other methods to generate hypoxanthine-based frameworks can be utilized in place of the Gewald reaction. The reaction utilizes the hydrolysis and further cyclization of 3-cyano-2-aminothiophene derivatives. Compound 2, compound 5 and compound 6 (Figure 29) were refluxed in formic acid to produce the thiophene pyrimidine derivatives with the framework of hypoxanthine-like in good yields.

Figure 29: Structures of compounds 2, 5 and 6.

Compound	Solvent, Temperature, Reaction time	Yield
18 	Formic Acid, Reflux, 36 hours	60%
19 	Formic Acid, Reflux, 24 hours	67%
20 	Formic Acid, Reflux, 24 hours	75%

Table 7: Hypoxanthine-like compounds synthesized, their yields and reaction conditions.

Thus, for the synthesis of hypoxanthine-like derivatives, conventional methods using the Gewald reaction scheme proved to be unsuccessful in the generation of desired 2-aminothiophene derivatives. This could have possibly been due to the low reactivity of cyanoacetamide in these types of cyclizations. Knoevenagel condensation of an activated nitrile and ketone to produce intermediate was also shown to be unsuccessful. Because of this, the synthesis of hypoxanthine-like compounds was accomplished by hydrolysis and further cyclization, in the presence of formic acid, of 3-cyano-2-aminothiophenes derivatives in moderately high yields.

2.1.4. SYNTHESIS OF 2-AMINOTHIOPHENE AND THIOPHENE PYRIMIDINE DERIVATIVES ON THE BASIS OF RIGID DIKETONES

Synthesis of compound 21 was shown to undergo two varying directions. Depending on the nature of the base present as the catalyst in the listed reaction conditions, compound 21 or 22 was formed (Figure 30). We have demonstrated that the use of an inorganic base promotes the synthesis of compound 22 in the presence of excess malononitrile. When organic bases are utilized, the synthesis of compound 21 is observed. The syntheses of both compounds are novel methods that have not been referenced previously in literature. Compound 21 was synthesized for the first time using the methods listed in Figure 30, while compound 22 has been previously synthesized using a three step procedure (Figure 31). The synthetic scheme that we designed is a one-pot synthesis that produces roughly similar yields to those found in the literature method.²²

Figure 30: Synthetic schemes for the synthesis of Compound 21 and Compound 22.

Figure 31: Compound 22 was originally synthesized using a three-step procedure illustrated above.²²

The synthesis of Compound 21 was optimized as seen in Table 8 with 51% yield. These reactions proceed in the presence of organic bases. It was shown that the equivalent of the base is an important component to the yield. Piperdine is being used at 1:1 equivalent to the ketone indanedione and thus, is acting more as a reagent in the reaction.

Solvent	Base	Base Equivalents	Reagent Equivalents	Reaction Conditions
3 mL EtOH	Piperdine	0.13 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 90°C 17 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Piperdine	1.0 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 90°C 17 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Morpholine	0.13 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 90°C 17 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Morpholine	1.0 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 90°C 17 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Morpholine	0.13 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 90°C 4 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Piperdine	0.13 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 90°C 4 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Cs ₂ CO ₃	0.13 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 60°C 17 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Cs ₂ CO ₃	0.13 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 60°C 17 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Piperdine	1.0 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 60°C 17 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Morpholine	1.0 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 60°C 17 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	K ₂ CO ₃	1.0 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 60°C 17 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	K ₂ CO ₃	0.13 mmol	1,2,2.2	Reflux, 60°-90°C 72 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Cs ₂ CO ₃	0.5 mmol	1,2,2.2	Reflux, 60°-90°C 72 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Cs ₂ CO ₃	0.13 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 60°-90°C 72 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Piperdine	0.13 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 90°C 16 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Piperdine	1.0 mmol	1,2,2.2	Reflux, 90°C 16 hrs, 51% yield
3 mL EtOH	Cs ₂ CO ₃	0.5 mmol	1,2,2.2	Reflux, 90°C 16 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	Cs ₂ CO ₃	0.13 mmol	1,2,2.2	Reflux, 90°C 16 hrs, Unsuccessful
3 mL EtOH	K ₂ CO ₃	0.5 mmol	1,1,1.1	Reflux, 90°C 17 hrs, Unsuccessful

Table 8: Optimization of 2-amino-8-oxo-8H-indeno[2,1-b]thiophene-3-carbonitrile.

Compound 23 was synthesized in a one-pot fashion in which an inorganic base was used to catalyze the reaction. The low yield of 11% could possibly be a result of low first stage production of the desired 2-aminothiophene, which would affect the overall yield of the final thiophene pyrimidine. Table 9 describes the reaction conditions attempted for compound 23.

Figure 32: Synthesis of compound 23.

Solvent	Base	Reaction Conditions
CH(OEt) ₃	K ₂ CO ₃	Reflux, 143°C 3 hrs
CH(OEt) ₃	K ₂ CO ₃	Reflux, 143°C 6 hrs
Formic Acid	K ₂ CO ₃	Reflux, 100°C 12 hrs
1.5 mL EtOH	K ₂ CO ₃	100°C 16 hrs →
1.5mL CH(OEt) ₃		143°C 3 hrs

Table 9: Optimization of reaction conditions for compound 23.

Compound	Base	Reaction Conditions	Yield
21 	Piperidine (1 mmol)	Ethanol, Reflux, 16 hrs	51%
22 	CS ₂ CO ₃	Ethanol, Reflux, 16 hrs	86%
23 	-	Formamide, Reflux, 2 hrs	61%
24 	K ₂ CO ₃	Ratio 1:11 Ethanol and CH(OEt) ₃ 90°C for ~16 hrs, then increased to 143°C for 2 hrs	11.8 %

Table 10: Library synthesized on the basis of diketone derivatives of indanedi-one, the reaction conditions and yields

The synthesis of 2-aminothiophene and thiopyrimidine derivatives based on the model reaction using cyclohexanone were unsuccessful for rigid, aryl diketones.

As a result, new reaction conditions were developed for the synthesis of hypoxanthine-like and adenine-like derivatives of indandione.

2.2. EVALUATION OF BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY FOR 2-AMINOTHIOPHENE AND THIOPHENE PYRIMIDINE LIBRARY

2.2.1. ANTI-CANCER ACTIVITY

All compounds were tested using MTT analysis, which measures a growth inhibitory concentration (GI₅₀). This measurement calculates the concentration for 50% of maximal inhibition of cell proliferation. Compounds were primarily tested against HeLa cell line (uterine cancer cell line) and some were tested against MCF-7 cell line (breast cancer cell line). Values under 10 µM are considered significantly biologically active. All compounds GI₅₀ values can be found in Table 11.

Compound	GI ₅₀ (µM)	
	HeLa (Uterine Cancer Cell Line)	MCF-7 (Breast Cancer Cell Line)
1	28.6 ± 1.587	54.2 ± 2.485
2	79.11 ± 1.971	-
3	10.073 ± 0.740	-
4	58.3557 ± 58.355	-
5	9.3546 ± 0.199	-
6	8.5264 ± 0.246	-
7	15.585 ± 1.091	-
8	6.0 ± 1.277	-
9	127.06 ± 33.567	-
10	49.00 ± 1.438	-
11	6.4553 ± 0.154	-
12	42.8624 ± 1.354	-
13	3.57 ± 0.842	-
14	13.5 ± 1.5474	-
15	163.34 ± 52.017	-
16	74.91 ± 8.072	-
17	103.14 ± 1.827	-
18	>100 ± 56.785	-
19	14.52 ± 0.734	-
20	31.71 ± 2.391	-
21	61.74 ± 8.342	>100 ± 20.268
22	64.18 ± 10.457	85.97 ± 23.486
23	66.28 ± 9.035	69.25 ± 30.781
24	74.562 ± 11.284	82.534 ± 15.087

Table 11: Compounds were tested against HeLa cell lines and MCF-7 cell lines. The corresponding GI₅₀ values are listed above.

2.2.2. STRUCTURE ACTIVITY RELATIONSHIPS (SAR) CONCERNING ANTI-CANCER ACTIVITY

SAR is a very useful tool in medicinal chemistry. It helps to understand the pharmacodynamics of how a ligand (drug) is interacting with its binding site. By modifying different regions of the molecule and observing the effect of the drugs change in biological activity we can better understand the optimal interaction of the binding site between drug and target. Based on the fusion of pharmacophores 2-aminothiophene and thiophene pyrimidine, the core structure was modified systematically for the synthesis of a library of analogs. By analyzing the biological activity (GI_{50}) of compounds tested from the library, important features that compliment the pharmacophore are employed and in turn, this can help to better understand the binding site to optimize the overall biological activity.

Initially the biological activity of compound 1 was measured and determined to have moderate activity against both HeLa and MCF-7 cell lines. It should be noted that compound 1 is rigid in structure (Figure 33). Compounds 23 and 24 (Figures 34 and 35), which are also rigid, show poor activity due to observed constraints on the geometry of the molecule (Figures 34 and 35). Given that the structures for compound 23 and compound 24 are rigid, there is an observed strain that affects the planar structure of the pharmacophore. This strain is due to the two ring system attached to the pharmacophore may have been due to its shape when binding to the target ultimately resulting in poor recognition between the active site and ligand that should be interacting with it and a decrease in biological activity.

Figure 33: MM2 energy minimization modeling of compound 1. Pharmacophore is planar.

Compound 23

Figure 34: MM2 energy minimization modeling of compound 23. Pharmacophore is extremely distorted.

Compound 24

Figure 35: MM2 energy minimization modeling of compound 24. Pharmacophore is extremely distorted.

The cyclization of 2-aminothiophenes to thiophene pyrimidine increased the biological activity by nearly two-fold for most compounds synthesized on the basis of acetophenone derivatives (Figure 36). Cyclization of para derivatives increased activity by nearly half fold suggesting that the interaction with the binding site is much tighter for thiophene pyrimidine derivatives than for 2-aminothiophenes. While compound 10 had poor activity against HeLa cells, certain modifications on the flexible ring improved and worsened this activity. Compounds that contained halogen substituents in the para-position showed an improved activity for 2-aminothiophenes starting at lowest activity with -F (compound 4), moderate activity for -Cl (compound 3) and strongest activity for -Br (compound 5) (Figure 37). This suggests that electron density is an important role in the interaction with the target at that position.

Compound 8 (Figure 38) showed GI₅₀ value of 6.0 μ M; which is the most biologically active compound for 2-aminothiophene derivatives. Cyclization of the

compound was intended to double the biological activity however, for this compound, majority of the activity was decreased. Poor solubility of the thiophene pyrimidine may play a role, but more likely there is sterical hindrance. It is possible that 2-aminothiophene derivatives have a looser interaction with the binding site; this allows them more flexibility to conform with the target effectively without much sterical hindrance. When cyclized, they have a stronger interaction with the binding site, which is extra sensitive to steric hindrance, the interaction between compound 16 and its target is therefore no longer favorable (Figure 38). When cyclized, there is an observed change in the geometry of the molecule on the attached aromatic ring. MM2 energy minimizations, which model compounds in their lowest energy state represented in three dimensional space, shows this change (Figure 39 and 40). Modifications involving substitutions in the meta-position of the aromatic ring showed improved activity for 2-aminothiophene, but again, when cyclized the activity was decreased. Because this same occurrence was observed in compound 8 when compared to its cyclized derivative compound 16 (Figure 38), it is possible that sterical hindrance exists with the binding site when derivatives are cyclized (Figure 41).

Figure 36: Compound 2 (2-aminothiophene) activity against HeLa cells vs compound 10 (thiophene pyrimidine).

Figure 37: Anticancer activities against HeLa cells for halogenated 2-aminothiophenes.

Figure 38: Anticancer activities against HeLa cells of compound 8 (2-aminothiophene) vs compound 16 (thiophene pyrimidine).

Figure 39: MM2 energy minimization modeling of compound 8. Compound is planar.

Figure 40: MM2 energy minimization modeling of compound 16. Compound is not planar.

Figure 41: Anticancer activities against HeLa cells of p-Br in comparison to m-Br for 2-aminothiophenes, adenine-like and hypoxanthine like thiophene pyrimidines.

As mentioned earlier, previous research has not explored the biological significance of 2-aminothiophenes. 2-aminopyrroles have been identified as novel pharmacophores.¹² Because of similarity in structure, it was hypothesized that the 2-aminothiophene framework may indeed be a novel pharmacophore and a new lead in the development of medicinal agents. This study confirms that a biologically significant parallel between 2-aminopyrrole and 2-aminothiophene structure exists, suggesting that the 2-aminothiophenes framework is also a novel pharmacophore. Most of the compounds showed a range of high to low micromolar anticancer activity. It was shown that the cyclization of 2-aminothiophenes to thiophene pyrimidine increased the antiproliferative activity nearly two-fold for most compounds suggesting that the fusion of 2-aminothiophene and pyrimidine pharmacophores is useful in drug design. Employment of this technique in the synthesis of biologically active compounds may prove to be useful in the development of novel medicinal compounds. SAR suggests that p-Br substitution in the aromatic ring of adenine-like compounds is the most favorable design for the interaction of the drug and the target.

13
GI₅₀: 3.57 uM

Figure 42: Structure of Compound 13.

2.2.3 ANTI-MICROBIAL ACTIVITY

Various compounds were tested against both gram-positive (*S. pyogenes*, *S. epidermis*) and gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*, *P. fluorescens*). None of the compounds showed any significant toxicity against the bacterial strains. Table 9 describes the results measured against gram-positive bacteria, while table 10 describes results measured against gram-negative.

Gram Positive Bacteria Organism	Compound	Activity (MIC)
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	1	>100 μ M
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	2	>100 μ M
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	3	>100 μ M
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	4	>100 μ M
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	8	>100 μ M
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	9	>100 μ M
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	11	>100 μ M
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	15	>100 μ M
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	21	>100 μ M
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	23	>100 μ M
<i>S. pyogenes</i>	24	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	2	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	3	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	4	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	5	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	6	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	7	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	8	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	9	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	10	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	11	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	12	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	13	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	14	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	15	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	16	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	17	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	18	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	19	>100 μ M
<i>S. epidermis</i>	20	>100 μ M

Table 12: Compounds were tested against gram-positive bacteria. MIC values are indicated above.

Gram Negative Bacteria Organism	Compound	Activity (MIC)
<i>E. coli</i>	1	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	2	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	3	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	4	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	5	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	6	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	7	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	8	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	9	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	10	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	11	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	12	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	13	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	14	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	15	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	16	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	17	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	18	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	19	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	20	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	21	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	22	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	23	>100 μ M
<i>P. fluorescens</i>	24	>100 μ M

Table 13: Compounds were tested against gram-negative bacteria. MIC values are indicated above.

2.2.4. ANTI-FUNGAL ACTIVITY

Compounds were tested against *Candida albicans*. Most did not show any significant activity, however, both compound 19 and compound 20 had moderate MIC value at 50 μ M. MIC values for all compounds are indicated in table 11.

Figure 43: Structures of Compounds 19 and 20.

Organism	Compound	Activity (MIC)
<i>C. albicans</i>	1	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	2	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	3	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	4	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	5	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	6	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	7	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	8	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	9	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	10	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	11	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	12	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	13	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	14	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	15	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	16	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	17	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	18	>100 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	19	50 μ M
<i>C. albicans</i>	20	50 μ M

Table 14: Compounds were tested against *C. albicans*. MIC values are indicated above.

2.2.5 ANTI-PARASITIC ACTIVITY

Compound 12 was also tested against a parasite called *Trypanosoma brucei*, which is responsible for African sleeping sickness. It showed no significant biological activity.

12

Figure 44: Structure of Compound 12.

The use of thiophenes and thiophene pyrimidine derivatives based on the designed framework in areas of anti-microbial and anti-parasitic may not be useful. All compounds were rendered non-active against gram-positive or gram-negative bacteria. Also there was no activity for a promising design against anti-parasitic. The synthesis

of more libraries based on SAR need to be developed to explore the potential of these types of compounds in the treatment of bacteria and parasites. Anti-fungal properties do exist in hypoxanthine-like compounds, but also SAR needs to be developed to improve current activities.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

3.1. CHEMICAL MATERIALS

3.1.1. CHEMICAL SYNTHESIS

All reagents solvents and catalyst were purchased from commercially available sources, Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA and Fisher Scientific, Pittsburg, PA, USA without further purification. All reactions were performed using dry, round-bottomed flasks open to the atmosphere or under nitrogen. Reactions were monitored using thin layer chromatography on TLC glass-backed plates that were pre-coated with silica gel (250 μm) from Sorbtech sorbent technologies, Nocross, GA, USA. Exposure to UV light via Spectroline ENF-260C Long/Short Wavelength Ultraviolet UV Lamp was utilized in order to visualize TLC plates. Flash column chromatography was performed using silica gel (32-63 μm , 60 \AA pore size) from Sorbtech sorbent technologies. ^1H and ^{13}C nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra were obtained from a Bruker 400 MHz spectrometer, where chemical shifts were reported in ppm relative to a standard (Trimethyl Silane, or TMS).

3.2. BIOLOGICAL TESTING

3.2.1. ANTI-CANCER

Toxicity was tested against HeLa (cervical cancer) cells (CCL-2, ATCC.org, Manassas, VA). The cells were grown in DMEM media with 4.5g/L glucose, L-glutamine, and sodium pyruvate (10-013-CV, Mediatech, Inc., Manassas, VA) with 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (F0926, Sigma-Aldrich LLC, St. Louis, MO), without antibiotics. MCF-7 (breast cancer) cells (HTB-22, ATCC.org, Manassas, VA) were grown in RPMI 1640 with L-glutamine (10-030-CV, Mediatech, Inc., Manassas, VA) with 10% FBS as with HeLa, without antibiotics, at 37 C in 5% CO₂ atmosphere. Cells were trypsinized, counted by hemocytometer, and plated at 4000 cells per well into 96 well plates for HeLa cell line, and for MCF7, cells were plated at 4000 cells per well into 96 well plates in 300 μl of media per well. Compounds tested were dissolved in DMSO at 50 or 100 mM and applied to cells at 100 μM final total highest concentration 24 hours after plating when cells were at approximately 50% confluency, in a total final volume of 200 μl media per well. 48 hours later, 20 μl of MTT (Thiazoyl Blue Tetrazolium Bromide 0793, Amresco LLC, Solon, OH) dissolved in PBS at 5mg/ml was added to each well and incubated at 37 C in 5% CO₂ for 2 hours, then media was aspirated from the wells and 200 μl of 100% DMSO was added to each well, mixed by pipetting 100 μl up and down four times, and

absorbance was read at 490 nm on a microplate reader (Molecular Devices LLC, Sunnyvale, CA). Treatments and controls were performed in quadruplicate and data analyzed with Microsoft Excel.

3.2.2. ANTI-MICROBIAL

S. pyogenes (ATCC: 19615) was grown in brain-heart infusion broth at 37°C for 24 hours, *E.coli* was grown in trypticase soy broth at 37°C for 15 hours, *S. Epidermis* (ATCC: 29854) was grown in trypticase soy broth at 37°C overnight and *P. fluorescens* (ATCC: 700830) was grown in nutrient broth at 30°C overnight. Growths were adjusted to the working concentration of 5×10^5 CFU/ mL treated with compounds starting at a concentration of 100 μ M, incubated overnight and viability determined via MTT staining. Compounds that were active at 100 μ M were further tested by serially diluting compounds starting from 100 μ M, incubated overnight, and viability determined via MTT staining. Either 50 μ g/mL Polymyxin B or 50 μ g/mL Vancomycin was used as a positive control for growth inhibition.

3.2.3. ANTI-FUNGAL

C. albicans (ATCC: 26555) was grown in yeast mold media at 37°C over night. Growths were adjusted to the working concentration of 5×10^5 CFU/ mL treated with compounds starting at a concentration of 100 μ M, incubated overnight and viability determined via MTT staining. Compounds that were active at 100 μ M were further tested by serially diluting compounds starting from 100 μ M, incubated overnight at 37°C, and viability determined via MTT staining 18~24 hours of incubation.

3.2.4. ANTI-PARASITIC

Assays of *Trypanosoma cruzi* (ATCC 30013) were conducted by growing cells at 25°C in ATCC® Medium 1029: LIT medium for 5 days (stationary), diluting 1:10 into fresh media, adding drugs are various concentrations, incubating for additional 5 days, and assessing cell viability by microscopy and MTT assay using an untreated control for comparison.

3.2.5. MM2-ENERGY MINIMIZATION CALCULATIONS

Using ChemBio 3D Ultra (released date: May, 2014). Compounds were subject to a molecular modeling technique used for force field calculations. MM2 more specifically is used for calculating properties of organic molecular models. Rotations around single bonds are described are potentials for H-bonds and torsion potential.

Using single point energy calculation for MM2 in the software produces the lowest energy confirmation in three dimensional space.

3.3. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS FOR 2-AMINOTHIOPHENE AND THIOPHENE PYRIMIDINE LIBRARY

3.3.1. MONOKETONE DERIVATIVES

Procedure for 5,6,7,8-Tetrahydrobenzo(b)thiopheno[2,3-d]pyrimidine-4-yl-amine (1) Under nitrogen, a solution of cyclohexanone (1.0mmol, 0.09815 g), malononitrile (1.0 mmol, .06606 g,) and elemental sulfur (1.1 mmol, 0.035g) were added to 5 mL of formamide and stirred at 90° C for 16 hours. The reaction mixture was then heated to refluxed (210°C) for 2 hours. Once the reaction mixture cooled, water was added to the flask in a ratio of 6:1 (water:formamide) and allowed to sit for one hour. Precipitate was collected by filtration and washed with water, ethanol and diethyl ether. The compound was then redissolved in a mixture of methylene chloride and methanol and absorbed onto silica. Flash Chromatography was utilized to separate out compound (1) using 20:1 methylene chloride: methanol. Yield 87%, mp 161°C decomp., ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ: 11.86 (bs, 2H), 8.33 (s, 1H), 2.4 (s, 2H), 1.72 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ: 159.50, 145.54, 131.22, 128.12, 114.41, 93.57, 23.93, 23.82, 23.02, 22.12.

Procedure for 2-amino-4-phenylthiophene-3-carbonitrile (2) A solution of acetophenone (1.0mmol, 0.1546 g), malononitrile (2.0 mmol, 0.1321 g) and elemental sulfur (2.1 mmol, 0.7000 g) were added to 3 mL of pyridine and refluxed (115° C) for 6 hours. Once the reaction mixture was cooled, pyridine was evaporated off under reduced pressure. The mixture was then redissolved in 5 mL of acetone and absorbed onto silica. Flash Chromatography was then utilized to separate out compound (2) using 7:1 Hexane: Ethyl acetate. Yield 50%, mp 162°C decomp., ¹H NMR (400 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ: 7.63-7.61 (d, J=8.0 Hz, 2H), 7.46-7.42 (t, J=16.0, 2H), 7.39-7.37 (d,

J=8.0, 1H), 6.60 (bs, 2H), 6.53 (s, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) δ : 165.62, 139.36, 134.84, 128.62, 127.86, 127.09, 115.65, 105.25, 85.72.

Procedure for 2-amino-4-(4-chlorophenyl)thiophene-3-carbonitrile (3) A solution of 4-chloroacetophenone (1.0mmol, 0.1201 g), malononitrile (2.0 mmol, 0.1321 g) and elemental sulfur (2.1 mmol, 0.7000 g) were added to 3 mL of pyridine and refluxed (115° C) for 3 hours. Once the reaction mixture was cooled, pyridine was evaporated off under reduced pressure. The mixture was then redissolved in 5 mL of acetone and absorbed onto silica. Flash Chromatography was then utilized to separate out compound (3) using 7:1 Hexane: Ethyl acetate. Yield 46%, mp 164°C decomp., ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ : 7.58-7.55 (t, J=12.0 Hz, 2H), 7.43-7.41 (t, J=8.52, 2 H), 6.44 (s, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CD_3OD) δ : 166.71, 137.97, 133.45, 133.38, 128.36, 128.30, 115.97, 105.07, 84.04.

Procedure for 2-amino-4-(4-fluorophenyl)thiophene-3-carbonitrile (4) A solution of 4-fluoroacetophenone (1.0mmol, 0.1381 g), malononitrile (2.0 mmol, 0.1321 g) and elemental sulfur (2.1 mmol, 0.7000 g) were added to 3 mL of pyridine and refluxed (115° C) for 3 hours. Once the reaction mixture was cooled, pyridine was evaporated off under reduced pressure. The mixture was then redissolved in 5 mL of acetone and absorbed onto silica. Flash Chromatography was then utilized to separate out compound (4) using 7:1 Hexane: Ethyl acetate. Yield 45%, mp 158°C decomp., ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ : 7.60-7.56 (m, J=14.12 Hz, 2H), 7.16-7.12 (t, J=17.6, 2H), 6.37 (s, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CD_3OD) δ : 166.58, 163.74, 161.29, 138.25, 131.15, 128.81, 128.73, 116.07, 115.09, 114.88, 104.57, 84.35.

Procedure for 2-amino-4-(4-bromophenyl)thiophene-3-carbonitrile (5)

4-Bromoacetophenone (1.0mmol, 0.1991 g), malononitrile (2.0 mmol, 0.1321 g) and elemental sulfur (2.1 mmol, 0.7000 g) were added to 3 mL of pyridine and refluxed (115° C) for 3 hours. Once the reaction mixture was cooled, pyridine was evaporated off under reduced pressure. The mixture was then redissolved in 5 mL of acetone and absorbed onto silica. Flash Chromatography was then utilized to separate out compound (5) using 7:1 Hexane: Ethyl acetate. Yield 47%, mp 178°C decomp. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ: 7.64-7.62 (d, J=8.0, 2H) 7.57-7.55 (t, J=8.0, 2H) 6.7 (bs, 2H), 6.60 s, 1H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ: 165.82, 137.95, 133.6, 131.87, 131.70, 128.98, 121.40, 115.49, 105.89, 85.33.

Procedure for 2-amino-4-(3-bromophenyl)thiophene-3-carbonitrile (6) A solution of 3-Bromoacetophenone (1.0mmol, 0.1991 g), malononitrile (2.0 mmol, 0.1321 g) and elemental sulfur (2.1 mmol, 0.7000 g) were added to 3 mL of pyridine and refluxed (115° C) for 3 hours. Once the reaction mixture was cooled, pyridine was evaporated off under reduced pressure. The mixture was then redissolved in 5 mL of acetone and absorbed onto silica. Flash Chromatography was then utilized to separate out compound (6) using 7:1 Hexane: Ethyl acetate. Yield 57%, mp 174°C decomp., .. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) 7.80-7.79 (t, J=4.0, 1 H), 7.63-7.57 (d, J=24.0, 1 H), 7.56-7.55 (d, J=4.0 Hz, 1H), 7.43-7.39 (t, J=16.0 Hz, 1 H), 6.67 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ: 165.82, 137.48, 136.98, 130.73, 130.57, 129.82, 125.99, 122.19, 115.40, 106.48, 85.30.

Procedure for 2-amino-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)thiophene-3-carbonitrile (7) 4-methoxyacetophenone (1.0mmol, 0.1502 g), malononitrile (2.0 mmol, 0.1321 g) and elemental sulfur (2.1 mmol, 0.7000 g) were added to 3 mL of pyridine and refluxed (115° C) for 4 hours. Once the reaction mixture was cooled, pyridine was evaporated off under reduced pressure. The mixture was then redissolved in 5 mL of acetone and absorbed onto silica. Flash Chromatography was then utilized to separate out compound (7) using 4:1 Hexane: Ethyl acetate. Yield 30%. ¹H NMR (400 MHz,

(CD₃)₂CO) δ : 7.56-7.54 (m, J=8 Hz, 2H), 7.01-6.98 (m, J=12 Hz, 2H), 6.54 (bs, 2H), 6.43 (s, 1H), 3.84 (s, 3H). ¹²C NMR (100 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ : 165.41, 159.62, 128.65, 128.28, 127.36, 113.96, 103.91, 85.82, 54.82.

Procedure for 2-amino-4-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)thiophene-3-carbonitrile (8)

3,4,5-trimethoxyacetophenone (1.0mmol, 0.2102 g), malononitrile (2.0 mmol, 0.1321 g) and elemental sulfur (2.1 mmol, 0.7000 g) were added to 3 mL of pyridine and refluxed (115° C) for 5 hours. Once the reaction mixture was cooled, pyridine was evaporated off under reduced pressure. The mixture was then redissolved in 5 mL of acetone and absorbed onto silica. Flash chromatography was then utilized to separate out compound (8) using 2:1 Hexane: Ethyl acetate. Due to difficulty of separation and for further purification of compound 2, preparative TLC was utilized to clean the sample received from the flash chromatography step. The TLC was run at varying polarities: Hexane: Ethyl acetate 7:1, 6:1, 5:1, 4:1, 3:1, 2:1 and finally 1:1. Band was separated from plate and washed with 75 mL of chloroform to yield compound (8). Yield 45%. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ : 6.92 (s, 2H), 6.59 (bs, 2H), 3.88 (s, 6H), 3.76 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ : 165.45, 153.49, 139.42, 138.25, 130.15, 115.85, 104.76, 104.71, 85.81, 59.67, 55.53.

Procedure for 2-amino-4-(pyridin-4-yl)thiophene-3-carbonitrile (9)

4-acetylpyridine (1.0mmol, 0.1211 g), malononitrile (2.0 mmol, 0.1321 g) and elemental sulfur (2.1 mmol, 0.7000 g) were added to 3 mL of pyridine and refluxed (115° C) for 5 hours. Once the reaction mixture was cooled, pyridine was evaporated off under reduced pressure. The mixture was then redissolved in 5 mL of acetone and absorbed onto silica. Flash chromatography was then utilized to separate out compound (9) using 2:1 Hexane: Ethyl acetate. Due to difficulty of separation and for further purification of compound 2, preparative TLC was utilized to clean the sample

received from the flash chromatography step. The TLC was run at varying polarities: Hexane: Ethyl acetate 7:1, 6:1, 5:1, 4:1, 3:1, 2:1 and finally 1:1. Band was separated from plate and washed with 75 mL of chloroform to yield compound (2). Yield 44%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) δ : 8.65-8.63 (d, $J=8.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.61-7.59 (d, $J=8.0$, 2H), 6.86 (s, 1H), 6.77 (bs, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) δ : 166.20, 150.24, 141.49, 136.35, 121.23, 115.3, 108.13, 84.59.

Procedure for 5-phenylthieno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amine (10) Under nitrogen, compound 2 was added to 2 mL of formamide and allowed to reflux for 2 hours. Once the reaction mixture cooled, water was added to the flask in a ratio of 6:1 (water:formamide) and allowed to sit for one hour. Precipitate was collected by filtration and the solution was extracted with 3 washes of 15 mL of chloroform. The extracted solution was then evaporated off under reduced pressure and redissolved in acetone. Preparative TLC running at a polarity of 4:1 methylene chloride: ethyl acetate was then utilized to purify the sample and yield compound (2). Yield: 61%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) δ : 8.35 (s, 1H), 7.56–7.55 (m, 6H), 7.38 (s, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) δ 168.02, 158.62, 154.02, 136.33, 135.29, 129.04, 128.94, 128.45, 120.43, 113.41.

Procedure for 5-(4-chlorophenyl)thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amine (11) Under nitrogen, compound 3 was added to 2 mL of formamide and allowed to reflux for 2 hours. Once the reaction mixture cooled, water was added to the flask in a ratio of 6:1 (water:formamide) and allowed to sit for one hour. Precipitate was collected by filtration and the solution was extracted with 3 washes of 15 mL of chloroform. The extracted solution was then evaporated off under reduced pressure and redissolved in acetone. Preparative TLC running at a polarity of 4:1 methylene chloride: ethyl acetate was then utilized to purify the sample and yield compound (3). Yield 67%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) δ : 8.35 (s, 1 H), 7.57 (s, 4H), 7.4336 (s, 1H), 5.94 (bs,

2H). ^{13}C NMR (100MHz $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) δ : 169.43, 159.86, 155.33, 136.22, 135.28, 135.22, 131.99, 130.22, 122.29, 114.45.

Procedure for 5-(4-fluorophenyl)thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amine (12) Under nitrogen, compound 4 was added to 2 mL of formamide and allowed to reflux for 2 hours. Once the reaction mixture cooled, water was added to the flask in a ratio of 6:1 (water:formamide) and allowed to sit for one hour. Precipitate was collected by filtration and the solution was extracted with 3 washes of 15 mL of chloroform. The extracted solution was then evaporated off under reduced pressure and redissolved in acetone. Preparative TLC running at a polarity of 4:1 methylene chloride: ethyl acetate was then utilized to purify the sample and yield compound (4). Yield 64%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) δ : 8.35 (s, 1H), 7.61-7.58 (m, $J=14$ Hz, 2H) 7.40 (bs, 2H), 7.34-7.30 (t, 17.52 Hz, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) δ : 168.94, 164.94, 162.50, 159.52, 154.95, 135.07, 133.411, 132.08, 132.00, 121.64, 116.64, 116.50, 114.28.

Procedure for 5-(4-bromophenyl)thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amine (13) Under nitrogen, compound 5 was added to 2 mL of formamide and allowed to reflux for 3 hours. Once the reaction mixture cooled, water was added to the flask in a ratio of 6:1 (water:formamide) and allowed to sit for one hour. Precipitate was collected by filtration and the solution was extracted with 3 washes of 15 mL of chloroform. The extracted solution was then evaporated off under reduced pressure and redissolved in acetone. Preparative TLC running at a polarity of 4:1 methylene chloride: ethyl acetate was then utilized to purify the sample and yield compound (5). Yield 67%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) δ : 8.35 (s, 1H), 7.73-7.71 (d, $J=8.0$, 2H) 7.51-7.49 (d, $J=8.0$, 2H), 7.43 (s, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) δ : 168.20, 158.61, 154.06, 135.36, 134.06, 131.94, 131.00, 122.15, 121.03, 113.12.

Procedure for 5-(3-bromophenyl)thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amine (14) Under nitrogen, compound 6 was added to 2 mL of formamide and allowed to reflux for 4 hours. Once the reaction mixture cooled, water was added to the flask in a ratio of 6:1 (water:formamide) and allowed to sit for one hour. Precipitate was collected by filtration and the solution was extracted with 3 washes of 15 mL of chloroform. The extracted solution was then evaporated off under reduced pressure and redissolved in acetone. Preparative TLC running at a polarity of 4:1 methylene chloride: ethyl acetate was then utilized to purify the sample and yield compound (6). Yield 68%.

Procedure for 5-(4-methoxyphenyl)thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amine (15) Under nitrogen, compound 7 was added to 2 mL of formamide and allowed to reflux for 2 hours. Once the reaction mixture cooled, water was added to the flask in a ratio of 6:1 (water:formamide) and allowed to sit for one hour. Precipitate was collected by filtration and the solution was extracted with 3 washes of 15 mL of chloroform. The extracted solution was then evaporated off under reduced pressure and redissolved in acetone. Preparative TLC running at a polarity of 4:1 methylene chloride: ethyl acetate was then utilized to purify the sample and yield compound (7). Yield 42%. 8.32 (bs, 2H), 7.43-7.38 (m, J=20 Hz, 3H), 7.38 (s, 1H), 7.10-7.07 (d, J=12.0, 1H), 3.83 (s, 3H).

Procedure for 5-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amine (16) Under nitrogen, compound 8 was added to 2 mL of formamide and allowed to reflux for 2 hours. Once the reaction mixture cooled, water was added to the flask in a ratio of 6:1 (water:formamide) and allowed to sit for one hour. Precipitate was collected by filtration and the solution was extracted with 3 washes of 15 mL of chloroform. The extracted solution was then evaporated off under reduced pressure and redissolved in

acetone. Preparative TLC running at a polarity of 4:1 methylene chloride: ethyl acetate was then utilized to purify the sample and yield compound (8). Yield 46%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) δ : 8.34 (s, 1H), 7.38 (s, 1H), 6.81 (s, 2H), 6.0 (bs, 2H), 3.90 (s, 6H), 3.80 (s, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) δ : 167.86, 158.58, 153.98, 153.70, 138.37, 135.44, 131.49, 120.08, 113.42, 106.44, 59.74, 55.66.

Procedure for 5-(pyridin-4-yl)thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-amine (17) Under nitrogen, compound 9 was added to 2 mL of formamide and allowed to reflux for 2 hours. Once the reaction mixture cooled, water was added to the flask in a ratio of 6:1 (water: formamide) and allowed to sit for one hour. Precipitate was collected by filtration and the solution was extracted with 3 washes of 15 mL of chloroform. The extracted solution was then evaporated off under reduced pressure and redissolved in acetone. Preparative TLC running at a polarity of 4:1 methylene chloride: ethyl acetate was then utilized to purify the sample and yield compound (9). Yield 52%. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ : 8.69 (s, 1H), 8.37 (s, 1H), 7.68 (s, 1H), 7.50-7.49 (d, $J=4.0$, 2H), 7.12 (bs, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ : 168.21, 158.74, 154.38, 150.44, 143.43, 133.08, 124.06, 123.33, 112.61.

Procedure for 5-phenylthieno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4(1H)-one (18) Compound 2 was added to 3 mL of formic acid and allowed to reflux for 36 hours. After the reaction was complete, the mixture was allowed to cool and half the solvent was removed from the flask using reduced pressure. Upon evaporation, a precipitate formed, which was filtered off using a frit funnel. Solid was washed with ethanol and diethyl ether to yield compound (18). Yield 72%. ^1H (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ : 8.15-8.14 (d, $J=4.0$ Hz, 1 H), 7.55-7.51 (m, $J=12.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.51 (s, 1H), 7.41-7.31 (m, $J=40$ Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ : 166.13, 157.81, 146.31, 139.02, 135.77, 129.79, 127.98, 127.77, 121.48, 121.31.

Procedure for 5-(3-bromophenyl)thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4(1H)-one (19)

Compound 6 was added to 3 mL of formic acid and allowed to reflux for 24 hours. After the reaction was complete, the mixture was allowed to cool and half the solvent was removed from the flask using reduced pressure. Upon evaporation, a precipitate formed, which was filtered off using a frit funnel. Solid was washed with ethanol and diethyl ether to yield compound (19). Yield 78%. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 8.16 (s, 1H), 7.73 (s, 1 H), 7.62 (s, 1H), 7.55-7.55 (d, J=8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.37-7.32 (t, J=20.0, 1 H).

5-(4-bromophenyl)thieno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4(1H)-one (20) Compound 5 was added to 3 mL of formic acid and allowed to reflux for 24 hours. After the reaction was complete, the mixture was allowed to cool and half the solvent was removed from the flask using reduced pressure. Upon evaporation, a precipitate formed, which was filtered off using a frit funnel. Solid was washed with ethanol and diethyl ether to yield compound (19). Yield 75%. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 12.53 (s, 1H), 8.16 (s, 1H), 7.59-7.57 (d, J=8.0, 2H), 7.50-7.48 (d, J=8.0, 2H).

3.3.2. DIKETONE DERIVATIVES

2-amino-8-oxo-8H-indeno[2,1-b]thiophene-3-carbonitrile (21) 1,3-Indanedione (1.0 mmol, 0.1461 g), malononitrile (2.0 mmol, 0.1321 g) and elemental sulfur (2.1 mmol, 0.7000 g) were added to 3 mL of ethanol and refluxed (90°) for 16 hours in the presence of a base, piperidine (1.0 mmol, 0.9878 mL). Once the reaction mixture cooled, the reaction mixture was poured onto cold water and was allowed to sit for one hour. Precipitate was collected by filtration and washed with water, ethanol and diethyl ether. The precipitate was recrystallized in ethanol and precipitate was collected by filtration yielding compound (10). Yield 51%. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 8.79 (bs, 2H), 7.41-7.39 (d, J=32.0, 1H), 7.33-7.28 (m, J=20 Hz, 3H).

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 182.62, 176.07, 158.76, 137.54, 137.11, 133.34, 130.07, 122.62, 119.42, 114.43, 114.00, 79.26.

2-(2-amino-3-cyano-8H-indeno[2,1-b]thiophene-8-ylidene)malononitrile (11) 1,3-Indanedione (1.0 mmol, 0.1461 g), malononitrile (2.0 mmol, 0.1321 g) and elemental sulfur (2.1 mmol, 0.7000 g) were added to 3 mL of ethanol and refluxed (90°) for 16 hours in the presence of a base, Cs_2CO_3 (0.5 mmol, 0.16291 g). Once the reaction mixture was cooled, a precipitate formed. This precipitate was filtered off washed with ethanol and diethyl ether yielding compound (11). Yield 86% ^1H (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 9.27 (bs, 2H), 7.78-7.76 (d, $J=8.0$, 1H), 7.41-7.37 (t, $J=16.0$, 1H), 7.33-7.29 (m, $J=16$, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 176.76, 155.57, 155.59, 138.20, 135.38, 132.80, 130.12, 124.50, 120.76, 115.55, 114.59, 114.47, 113.65, 80.80, 64.48.

9-oxo-8H-indeno-thieno[2,3-b]pyrimidin-4-amine (23) Compound 10 was added to 2 mL of formamide and refluxed (210°C) for 2 hours. Once the reaction mixture cooled, water was added to the flask in a ratio of 6:1 (water: formamide) and allowed to sit for one hour. Precipitate was collected by filtration and washed with water, ethanol and diethyl ether. The compound was then redissolved in acetone and absorbed onto silica. Flash Chromatography was utilized to separate out compound (11) using 4:1 methylene chloride: ethyl acetate. Yield 61%.

9-oxo-8H-indeno-thieno[2,3-b]pyrimidin-4-one (24) Under Nitrogen, 1,3-Indanedione (1.0 mmol, 0.1461 g), cyanoacetamide (2.0 mmol, 0.1682 g) and elemental sulfur (2.1 mmol, 0.7000 g) were added to a mixture of 2.5 mL of ethanol and 2.5 mL of triethyl orthoformate in the presence of a base, K_2CO_3 (0.5 mmol, 0.16291 g). The reaction mixture was heated to 90°C for 16 hours. At that point, the temperature was increased to the reflux temperature of triethyl orthoformate (146°C) for 3 hours. Once the reaction cooled, triethyl orthoformate was evaporated under reduced pressure. The reaction mixture was redissolved into 2 mL of dimethylformamide and absorbed onto silica. Flash Chromatography was utilized to separate out compound (11) using 2:1 methylene chloride: ethyl acetate. Yield 13%. 1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 13.01 (bs, 1H), 8.29 (s, 1H) 8.05-8.03 (d, J=8.0, 1H), 7.54-7.45 (m, J=36.0, 2H), 7.32-7.28 (t, J=16.0, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 190.29, 189.63, 166.57, 140.38, 130.66, 128.95, 118.29, 107.84.

4. CONCLUSION

We have developed a new modification of existing Gewald reaction conditions that allows for the incorporation of aromatic ketones in the synthesis of frameworks based off of nucleic bases hypoxanthine and adenine from commercially available reagents. This modification allowed for the synthesis of a total of twenty four compounds with designed structures 2-aminothiophene and thiophene pyrimidine. From these compounds, twenty of them are novel. Compounds also showed very interesting anti-cancer and anti-fungal activity. It was found that cyclized derivatives had improved anticancer activity over their 2-aminothiophene counterparts for most derivatives. It also was found that compounds containing lipophilic, halogen substituents in the para position were the most active concerning anticancer activity. p-Br and m-Br substituents in the aromatic ring based on hypoxanthine-like framework had the best activity against the fungus *C. albicans*. Compounds showed no activity against gram positive and gram negative bacteria as well as *trypanosoma brucei*.

Evidence obtained indicates that the fusion of pharmacophores is a useful technique in the development of novel, biologically active compounds. It was also shown that 2-aminothiophenes are novel pharmacophores, which is also useful in the development of new medical agents. Future studies involve the evaluation of SAR for improving activity in anti-fungal and anticancer areas.

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APPENDIX: NMR CHARACTERIZATION

Lindsay2aminophe1-16-13H 1 1 C:\Bruker\TOPSPIN2.1.6 Sean
Lindsay2aminophe1-16-13H

¹H- (CD₃)₂CO
 400 MHz

¹H- (CD₃)₂CO
 400 MHz

^{13}C - $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$
 100 MHz

$^1\text{H}-(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$
 400 MHz

^{13}C - $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$
100 MHz

¹H- (CD₃)₂CO
 400 MHz

^{13}C - $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$
 100 MHz

¹³C- DMSO
 100 MHz

